

ESCHERICHIA COLI URINARY INFECTION – A PROTOCOL FOR THE TREATMENT OF MEDICINAL BIOMAGNETISM

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Urinary tract infection (UTI) has been a major driver of drug costs in public and private health systems, with *Escherichia coli* being the main etiological agent. Medicinal Biomagnetism (MB) is based on the application of therapeutic magnets for the treatment of various dysfunctions resulting from magnetic fields generated by biological systems, and can be an alternative complementary method for UTIs. **Objective and Method:** Through an exploratory literature review, the objective of this work was to present a protocol for complementary treatment of *E. coli* UTI, consisting of Biomagnetic Pairs (BMP) and developed from the complete scanning of MB. **Results:** Based on the complete scanning, which leads to the bioenergetic and biomagnetic diagnosis of various pathologies, including the application of protocols, it was found that MB contributes to the complementary treatment of UTIs. **Conclusion:** Although

successful experiences of MB have been observed in more complex areas than the urinary tract, more studies – with a larger number of tests and diversity of occurrences – are recommended to provide greater consistency and credibility to the results, as well as to envision the possibility of discoveries for new applications of this type of treatment.

Keywords: Medical Biomagnetism; Biomagnetic Pair; Medical Biomagnetism Protocol; Static Magnetic Fields; Magnets; Urinary Tract Infection; *Escherichia coli*.

1. INTRODUCTION

Urinary tract infections (UTIs) are defined as the invasion and multiplication of microorganisms in the tissues of the urinary system. It may be classified according to their topography: upper, when it involves the renal parenchyma (pyelonephritis) or ureters (urethritis); and lower, when affects the bladder (cystitis), ureters (urethritis), and, in men, the prostate (prostatitis) and epididymis (epididymitis) (JÚNIOR et al., 2018).

Women are the most affected by UTIs considering that the most recurring pathogen is *Escherichia coli* detected in about 80% of all infection cases. This is due to aspects related to the virulence of the bacteria and the susceptibility of the host, which allow for better adhesion and colonization of microorganisms (HADDAD, 2019).

Junior and colleagues (2018) state that UTI is the most common infections in Brazil with the extreme importance in the scope of laboratory demands. In addition, UTIs stand out among a large part of basic care services, including emergency and urgency care. In the following topics, some particularities of UTI caused by *E. coli* and alternative methods for its treatment will be presented.

1.1. URINARY TRACT INFECTION CAUSED BY *Escherichia coli*

E. coli is the main etiological agent of urinary tract infections and is responsible for most of the drug costs in public and private health systems. It tends to decrease productivity at work due to the morbidity generated (KORB et al., 2013).

This infection disease may be characterized as asymptomatic or symptomatic, and its complexity, concerning uropathogenic *E. coli*, depends on the immunity of the host, bacterial load, and virulence factor (COSTA, 2019). Part of the patients are at higher risk of developing complications due to undiagnosed UTI (FERREIRA et al., 2022). The estimated patient profile is 0.5 episodes of acute cystitis in young women per person/year (HADDAD, 2019).

The knowledge of its morphophysiology and pathogenicity mechanisms helps in the prevention and treatment of these infections. Several studies carried out in the emergency departments in Brazil show the incidence of *E. coli* cases; more than 50% of the affected population showed resistance to antimicrobials (KORB et al., 2013).

Alanazi and colleagues (2018) highlight that to trigger the infectious process, microorganisms (*E. coli*) reach the urinary tract by an ascending, hematogenous, or lymphatic route. According to clinical data, 95% of UTIs occur due to the ascension of infectious agents from the urethra to the bladder, thus reaching the renal medulla.

There are some complementary practices to traditional medicine using Static Magnetic Fields (SMF) to assist the treatment of urinary tract infections caused by *E. coli*. Next, we may discuss static magnetic fields and some effects on living beings.

1.2. STATIC MAGNETIC FIELDS (SMF)

Magnetism is one of the four fundamental forces of nature. This phenomenon results from the movement of electric particles, which indicates a close relationship between magnetism and electricity (DURÁN and MARTÍNEZ, 2014). Tipler and Mosca (2006) drew attention to the fact that, although electric charges and magnetic poles have several similarities, there is a significant difference between them: magnetic poles always occur in pairs. The division of a magnet in two parts results in equal and opposite poles, each identified with a north and a south pole.

All matter presents manifestations of magnetism, from the imperceptible, through the subtle, including forces of the great magnitude. The different magnetic properties of materials with reaction to the magnetic field provides their classification into diamagnetic (magnetic moment in the opposite direction to the field, referring to substances or elements that have no affinity with magnetism); paramagnetic (producing magnetic moment that adds to the magnetic field referring to substances or elements that have an affinity with magnetism); and ferromagnetic (zero magnetic moment, when magnetic fields are formed by distortion of organic pH) (DURÁN and MARTÍNEZ, 2014 – Figure 1).

Figure 1 – The differences in magnetic propriety of materials

Type of magnetism	Magnetising field is absent ($H = 0$)	Magnetising field is present ($H \neq 0$)
Diamagnetism	 (Aligned opposite to the field)	
Paramagnetism	 (Aligned with the field)	
Ferromagnetism	 (Aligned with the field)	

Adapted from https://www.brainkart.com/article/Classification-of-Magnetic-Materials_38453/

Marycz, Kornicka & Röcken (2018) define a SMF as a constant and unchanging vector field that exerts a magnetic influence on living or non-living matter due to electric currents and magnetic materials. Carneiro and colleagues (2000) emphasise that magnetic fields in biological systems arise from ionic currents that flow during cell depolarization; it would occur in paramagnetic substances

that make up living systems, and in ferromagnetic substances that are used as magnetic markers or that contaminate these systems.

In addition, Albuquerque and colleagues (2016) highlight that the SMF affects cellular systems. Considering that the magnetic field only acts on elements with specific sensitivity to it (presenting magnetic dipoles), the effects are expected to be non-deterministic in complex systems, such as the cellular environment. Exposure to the SMF certainly triggers cellular effects but with high unpredictability.

Therefore, if a cell culture is subjected to a vertical magnetic field for a long time, the appearance of the cells may change during this process (TENG, 2005). Depending on the combination of types of electric charges (ions, free electrons) and molecules, and considering that the cellular environment does not originate from a linear system, cellular responses may be produced, giving rise to magnetism-dependent phenomena (ALBUQUERQUE et al., 2016).

Silva and colleagues (2016) demonstrated that the SMF through the use of magnet therapy provides a reduction in joint stiffness – initially, the improvement in pain was a consequence of the action of the electromagnetic field on the cell. In another example, the study developed by Perez (2022) concluded that horizontal SMF composed by neodymium magnets increase cell proliferation of NIH3T3 fibroblasts by approximately 53%, verified after 24 hours of exposure to moderate magnetic fields.

Medicinal Biomagnetism (MB), an integrative complementary technique that uses SMF generated by medium-intensity magnets aims to balance the body's bioelectromagnetic field.

1.3. MEDICINAL BIOMAGNETISM (MB)

Medicinal Biomagnetism (MB) is a therapeutic system developed in 1988 by the Mexican doctor and physiotherapist Isaac Goiz Durán. It is based on the application of therapeutic magnets for the treatment of dysfunctions caused by magnetic fields generated on biological systems. The goal of the application is to

achieve the bioelectric balance of tissues, organs, and systems through the application of SMF generated by magnets to reverse the polarization of charges that maintain the Biomagnetic Pairs (BMP) (DURÁN, 2008).

As Carneiro et al. (2000) describe, this technique addresses the interface of physics with biology studying the magnetic fields produced by living organisms. The non-invasive procedure is one of the main reasons for the adoption of biomagnetic treatment using magnetic materials on the external regions of the body.

Studies preceding the development of MB were done by Richard Broeringmeyer (1991) which discovered that dysfunctions in organs are mainly generated by pH distortions. Broeringmeyer did not attribute therapeutic value to the fact that the polarization state of charges generated by pH distortions should be undone, i.e., the SMF generated by magnets should be applied to undo the polarization state of charges that maintain the BMP. It suggests that they had not yet reached the concept of the BMP or this procedure was not permitted in your country (BROERINGMEYER, 1991; DURÁN, 2003, 2008; DURÁN and MARTÍNEZ, 2014).

According to Broeringmeyer's theory (1991) combined with the idea of the Law of Universal Magnetism it was possible to undo the polarization state of charges. It becomes possible by applying a field of opposite polarity to the bioenergetic field produced by organisms, in order to attract hydrogen ions and free radicals of opposite polarity. The same study also highlighted that there could be secondary dysfunctions related to the polarization processes of internal organs that (1) in the case of positive charged poles, would produce functional excitation, and (2) in the case of negative polarity, a decrease in their normal function (BROERINGMEYER, 1991; DURÁN, 2008).

After the first biomagnetism course offered by the Society of Alternative Medicine in Guadalajara that Richard Broeringmeyer presented the basis of therapeutic energy (*The Biomagnetic Man*), while Isaac Goiz Durán developed the BMP initiating the principles of energetic therapy (DURÁN, 2008). Thus, the BMP was initially used to confirm that the bioenergetic polarization of an organ

reveals degenerative processes in the short or medium term. The concept of magnetic poles discovered by Broeringmeyer together with quantitative and indirect measurement through medium-intensity magnets became the basis of the method developed by Isaac Goiz Durán. This knowledge led to the understanding of organic pathologies from the bioenergetics perspective. In addition, it contributed to build clinical correlations and treatments through magnetic fields, with or without the association of other therapeutic procedures of pharmacological or surgical order (BROERINGMEYER, 1991; DURÁN, 2008).

Thus, in Isaac Goiz Durán's (2008) definition, the Biomagnetic Pair is:

"It is the set of charges that identify a pathology in which is composed of two main charges of opposite polarity; this is built from the functional alteration of the pH of the organs that support it. From this bioenergetic duality, another fundamental principle could be extracted, The Normal Energetic Level (NEL), which defines the bioenergetic limits responsible for all cellular metabolic processes of human organisms, depending on the temperature (entropy)."
(DURÁN, 2008).

According to Durán (2008), there are eight groups of biomagnetic pairs: 1) Regular Pairs, which group common pathologies supported by a single microbiological entity, such as viruses, bacteria, fungi, or parasites; 2) Special Pairs, which refer to organ or system dysfunctions without the presence of pathogenic microorganisms; 3) Dysfunctional Pairs, specifically related to internal secretion glands; 4) Complex Pairs, which define some dysfunctional pathologies that affect other systems or tissues; 5) Reservoir Pairs, where pathogenic microorganisms can be lodged for an indefinite period; 6) Temporary Pairs, mainly formed by traumas, which is eliminated spontaneously when the patient is cured; 7) Associated Pairs, which are defined by chronic-degenerative,

syndromic, tumor pathologies, and all pathologies that do not fit into a single pathogenic microorganism; and 8) Reciprocal Pairs, which have a double charge on each pole.

Usually magnets greater than 1,000 Gauss to neutralize the double polarity, since the body behaves like a dielectric; it is possible to return to the NEL. It means that either the NEL or another dielectric artifact act on the formation and stability of each BMP, allowing a return to homeostasis, an aspect considered in bioenergetics. It is also found that BM studies, detects, classifies, and corrects pH alterations in humans (DURÁN, 2008).

Studies developed by Durán (2008) demonstrated that the magnetic fields between 1,000 and 50,000 Gauss do not represent toxicity in BMP. Thus, the biomagnetic therapy could be a complementary procedure understanding the disease from the energy, vibration, and chemical point of view. The magnetic field is not what cures but what provides adjustment of altered pH through the use of magnets.

In summary, biomagnetic therapy consists of impacting, with magnets above 1,000 Gauss, the poles built in the body that sustain the polarization of the charges in dysfunctional biochemical elements. This phenomenon aims to move them until the collision of the opposite charges (positive and negative), thus returning to homeostasis (NEL) (DURÁN and MARTÍNEZ, 2014).

Through this diagnosis method called bioenergetic scanning, BM identifies where the magnets should be applied to undo the polarization of the charges sustaining BMP. Over this concept it is possible to identify the affected organ, its polarity, the organ with which it resonates, the identification of the microorganism that generates it, and to proceed the reversion of the BMP through the application of magnets (DURÁN and MARTÍNEZ, 2014).

1.4. MEDICINAL BIOMAGNETISM IN THE TREATMENT OF URINARY INFECTION CAUSED BY *E. Coli*

Medicinal Biomagnetism (MB) performs bioenergetic and biomagnetic diagnosis for the treatment of pathologies. MB includes the application of specific protocols that collaborate in a complementary or alternative way in glandular, immunological, intoxication dysfunctions, and in the pathogenesis of UTI caused by *E. coli*. It is a complementary integrative technique that may contribute to the treatment and prevention of UTI caused by *E. coli* (DURÁN, 2008).

Microorganisms tend to fill spaces in the tissues changing the pH of the reticuloendothelial system. This condition directly affects the cells causing changes in the biological cycle, generating "Pus" which must be removed by the lymphatic system or used as a nutrient for pathogenic parasites generally feeding on bacteria or their exudates (DURÁN, 2003).

The pathogenicity of a bacteria is mainly recognized by the resonance caused by the structural virus at the opposite pole of BMP, secondarily to the place where it is located (DURÁN, 2008). Once the North pole of the BMP for urinary infection by *E. coli* is found their resonance (South pole) is immediately identified by bioenergetics. When impacted by MB, the *E. coli* bacteria and its RNA virus resonator are eliminated due to the neutralization of pH. The BMP generated by *E. coli* treatment is called Indicator/Indicator, which can be located either right/left or left/right (DURÁN, 2008).

Urinary infection caused by *E. coli* is highly prevalent, especially in the females, and its treatment is usually with antibiotic therapy. This technique has a high cost and sometimes is not effective for the complete remission of the infection. For example, repeated urinary infections tend to originate selected resistance strains through drugs used in antibiotic therapy. In this case, the use of probiotics may be a better alternative for the treatment of UTIs (GEERLINGS, 2016).

The option for using the MB technique include benefits such as the few contraindications, non-invasive method, low-cost, and painless. In addition, this technique is supported by the fact that major actions taken by the pharmaceutical industry to restore health have not taken into account the

organic, psychological, and environmental changes of the individual (DURÁN, 2008).

Considering the repeated urinary infections caused by *E. coli*, a fact associated with antibiotic resistance, the aim of this work is to present a protocol created by Isaac Goiz Durán consisting of biomagnetic pairs supported by the complete scanning procedure of Medicinal Biomagnetism as a complementary treatment for UTI caused by *E. coli*.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study may be characterized as exploratory bibliographic review because it was developed using published books and scientific articles. The exploratory research was applied to this study because it is a method that contributes to greater familiarity with the topic of interest, making it clearer and constructing pivotal hypotheses (GIL, 2002). The literature review was conducted on the central subject and related themes to clarify and validate the initial aim of the article. Then, the collected material was screened to select suitable publications. After that, a careful and analytical reading of the 24 selected publications was carried out resulting in the content of this article.

This study is based on the evidence by Isaac Goiz Durán, the pioneer to use bioenergetic therapy in biological systems. However, studies developed by Carneiro and colleagues (2000) were also analysed which tested the methodology of Biomagnetism in the field of cardiology, the functioning of the human brain, and the digestive system. The purpose to approach this work is due to the usefulness of magnetic fields measured in humans and investigations developed by the study groups working in this field in Brazil. According to this evidence it is possible to estimate more accurate localization of the region in the body that is applied the current intensity or concentration of paramagnetic or ferromagnetic materials.

3. RESULTS

The data collection for this study used scientific sources, mainly *ScienceDirect*, *Scielo*, *PubMed*, and the *Virtual Health Library* (BVS). Research articles and documents associated with universities and healthcare organizations were also consulted. The search used descriptors directly associated with the article's theme: *E. coli*; biomagnetism; Medicinal Biomagnetism; UTI; urinary tract infection; Par Biomagnetic; integrative and complementary therapies.

Publications and documents related to the proposed theme of the study were selected. Only full studies available in Portuguese, Spanish, and English published since 2008; this period was used because the theme is quite specific and the main author has older publications (not updated). Therefore, it was accepted to approach some studies from the same year.

A careful analysis and selection of studies that actually met the guiding question of the article was then made. It resulted in 24 publications, including books, research articles, manuals, and related documents. Table 1 shows the list of publications analyzed but not used in this article.

TYPE	AUTHORS	YEAR	TITLE	SOURCE
Article	Melo A V, Sant'Ana G R, Bastos P R H O	2022	Redes, atores e agenciamentos na constituição da Política de Práticas Integrativas e Complementares no Brasil	DOI: 10.1590/1413-8123202276.16442021
Article	Machado G, Marinho A, Afonso J, Freitas M, Silva M, Coelho R	2022	Infecções do trato urinário nos cuidados de saúde primários: estado da arte	DOI: 10.32385/rpmgf.v38i2.13337
Article	Silva JL, Silva MR, Ferreira SM, Rocha RM, Barbosa DA	2022	Resistência microbiana a medicamentos em uma Instituição de Longa Permanência para Idosos	DOI: http://dx.doi.org/10.37689/acta-ape/2022AO03751
Article	Cardoso, RF; Lacerda, ACR; Lima, VP; de Oliveira, LFF; de Oliveira, SFF; Araújo, RP; Castro, CLFe; da Silva, FP; de Paiva, LV; Dietrich, L.; et al.	2022	Eficácia da Acupuntura na Qualidade de Vida, Desempenho Funcional, Dispneia e Função Pulmonar em Pacientes com Doença Pulmonar Obstrutiva Crônica: Protocolo para um Ensaio Clínico Randomizado	DOI: https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm11113048
Article	Marcos-Carbajal P, Salvatierra G, Yareta J, Pino J, Vásquez N, Díaz P, et al.	2021	Caracterización microbiológica y molecular de la resistencia antimicrobiana de <i>Escherichia coli</i> uropatógenas de hospitales públicos peruanos.	DOI: https://doi.org/10.17843/rpmesp.2021.381.6182
Report	Gerência de Vigilância e Monitoramento em Serviços de Saúde – GVIMS Gerência Geral de Tecnologia em Serviços de Saúde – GGTS Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária – ANVISA	2021	Programa Nacional de Prevenção e Controle de Infecções relacionadas à assistência à saúde (PNPCIRAS) 2021 a 2025	< https://www.gov.br/anvisa/pt-br/centraisdeconteudo/publicacoes/servicosdesaude/publicacoes/pnpciras_2021_2025.pdf >.

Article	Neugent ML, Hulyalkar NV, Nguyen VH, Zimmern PE, De Nisco NJ	2020	Avanços na compreensão da urina humana microbioma e seu potencial papel na infecção do trato urinário	DOI: https://doi.org/10.1128/mBio.00218-20
Article	Yazdanpour, Z., Tajrobehkar, O. & Shahkhah, M.	2020	Significant association between genes encoding virulence factors with antibiotic resistance and phylogenetic groups in community acquired uropathogenic <i>Escherichia coli</i> isolates	DOI: https://doi.org/10.1186/s12866-020-01933-1
Report	World Health Organization (WHO)	2019	Minimum requirements for infection prevention and control	https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/330080/9789241516945-eng.pdf?ua=1
Article	Mendes DS, Moraes FS, Lima GO, Silva PR, Cunha TA, Crossetti MGO, et al.	2019	Benefícios das práticas integrativas e complementares no cuidado de enfermagem.	DOI: http://dx.doi.org/10.30681/252610103452
Article	Wassenaar, T. M.	2018	<i>E. coli</i> and colorectal cancer: a complex relationship that deserves a critical mindset	DOI: 10.1080/1040841X.2018.1481013
Article	Thomas A. Waller, Sally Ann L. Pantin, Ashley L. Yenior, George G.A. Pujalte, MD	2018	Urinary Tract Infection Antibiotic Resistance in the United States	DOI: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pop.2018.05.005
Article	Capone, F. et al.	2017	Um estudo aberto, de um braço, de escalonamento de dose para avaliar a segurança e a tolerabilidade de campos magnéticos de frequência em agudos acidente vascular cerebral isquêmico	DOI: 10.1038/s41598-017-12371-x
Report	World Health Organization (WHO)	2016	Guidelines on core components of infection prevention and control programmes at the national and acute health care facility level	https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/251730/9789241549929-eng.pdf
Article	Stevanato Filho, P R et al.	2015	Surgical complications and metachronous rectal cancer risk in patients with classic familial adenomatous polyposis	DOI: http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jcol.2015.01.006
Article	Pacheco AR, Sperandio V.	2014	Enteric pathogens exploit the microbiota-generated nutritional environment of the gut.	DOI: 10.1128/microbiolspec.MBP-0001-2014
Article	Markov MS	2014	Campos Eletromagnéticos e Vida	DOI: 10.4172/2332-0796.1000119
Article	Christian-Daniel Köhler, Ulrich Dobrindt	2011	What defines extraintestinal pathogenic <i>Escherichia coli</i> ?	DOI: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmm.2011.09.006

Article	Narciso, Ana & Lito, Luis & J, Melo-Cristino & Duarte, Aida	2010	Uropathogenic <i>Escherichia coli</i> : Antibiotic Resistance Versus Virulence Factors.	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/260310419_Uropathogenic_Escherichia_coli_Antibiotic_Resistance_Versus_Virulence_Factors
Article	Chandrasekaran S, Price N D	2010	Probabilistic integrative modelling of genome-scale metabolic and regulatory networks in <i>Escherichia coli</i> and <i>Mycobacterium tuberculosis</i>	www.pnas.org/lookup/suppl/doi:10.1073/pnas.1005139107/-/DCSupplemental
Book	Palandi J, Figueiredo D B, Porto A V. L, Denardin, J C, Magnago P R	2003	Eletromagnetismo	http://coral.ufsm.br/gef/arquivos/eletmag.pdf

Source: The authors

Table 2 summarises the amount and publication modalities that composed the content of this work. The respective data from these documents are related and recorded in the list of bibliographic references at the end of this article.

TABLE 2 – Titles and Publications		
All studies were divided by publication modality after applied the inclusion criteria 24 studies included		
5 Research Articles, Undergraduate Works and Master's Dissertations	10 Reports from Universities	9 Books and manuals

3.1. PROTOCOL

According to Durán (2008), the basis of biomagnetic diagnosis begins with the identification of biomagnetic poles, starting the scanning with the North or negative pole of the magnet. The best way to track the magnetic poles is usually with the patient in a dorsal decubitus position with the feet off on a flat base. Thus, the shortening or lengthening of the right leg could be evaluated. This system of diagnosis and evaluation using magnets is based on the principle of Intelligent Muscle Response, a method of Kinesiology that stimulates shortening or lengthening of the legs (DURÁN, 2008).

For the treatment of urinary tract infection caused by *E. coli*, the Regular Biomagnetic Pairs is recommended, based on the protocol: Indicator/Indicator; Thymus/Rectum; all fingers of the hand/contralateral (Thumb/Thumb, Middle Finger/Middle Finger, Ring Finger/Ring Finger, Little Finger/Little Finger) presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2 – Scanning points for the UTI treatment caused by *E. coli*

Illustrative image of the anatomical points that make up the Biomagnetic Pairs with the magnets applied to the body. The red colour represents the North pole applied to the skin. The black color represents the South pole applied. Source:

Bossa (2021)

The recommendation is to perform a complete scanning in the first session. The duration of the protocol impact, duration in days, and the number of times to impact need to be investigated through bioenergetics. After both this period and the remission of the symptoms, a new laboratory test is requested to investigate the absence of the bacteria.

4. DISCUSSION

According to the bibliographic reviews approached in this study referred to Medicinal Biomagnetism and urinary tract infection caused by *E. coli* is possible to affirm both the action of static magnetic fields in living and in human cells (ALBUQUERQUE et al. 2016). Regarding the development and corroboration of Medicine and Complementary Integrative Practices, the related literature allowed us to achieve the aim of defining a protocol that contributes to the treatment of UTIs, which have a high prevalence in population. Furthermore, the allopathic medicine to treat this disease includes high costs and low efficiency in positive results; often occurring recurrent infections despite the use of antimicrobials (FERREIRA et al. 2022).

The study developed by Frank (2017) used MB in infections by pathogens, in just one session, lasting 3 to 5 minutes of magnet impaction, as an alternative tool in the treatment of 13 people who tested positive for *Salmonella typhi* infection. The patients were retested with the same laboratory tests two days after the application of the magnets; at the end, 10 of the 13 patients who received MB treatment tested negative for *Salmonella typhi*.

The proposal of the protocol presented in this article is to offer an alternative treatment of UTIs, using a non-invasive, low-cost, and reproducibly easy-to-apply technique to improve not only the patients' health but also their physical, emotional, and energetic balance. As described in Durán's study, magnetic energy corrects pH distortions in organs, systems, and glands (DURÁN, 2008).

Undoubtedly, the scientific evolution of conventional treatments to improve the health of population is great in relevance, however, investing and testing new complementary and integrative treatments is a path that should bring future benefits – “We need to disentangle ourselves from the Manichean views of medical therapies, in which only one point of view is correct and is the best” (LUZ, 2019; LIMA, 2009).

Therefore, current research for this approach presents difficulties in clinical validation requiring more scientific investigation since it is still not allowed to

apply the protocol in clinical trials, which would lead to scientific validation.

5. CONCLUSION

Previous studies and the application of the Medicinal Biomagnetism techniques by the pioneer Isaac Goiz Durán attest to the effectiveness of this type of treatment as a complement and/or contribution in elucidating a myriad of diseases. The possibility of being applied in some cases (cardiopathies, neuropathies, gastroenterology) as well as in the development of technologies related to the technique – especially magnetic sensors – also generate positive expectations. Thus, the application of this protocol in experimental clinical studies is mandatory in order to evaluate its performance in the treatment of urinary tract infection caused by *E. coli*.

6. PERSPECTIVES

Considering the direct application for UTIs, even though successful results of MB in other areas (heart, brain) it is suggested to carry out more studies, especially practical ones, in order to provide greater consistency and credibility to the results. This body of evidence about MB and UTIs gives expectations to discover new applications for this type of treatment.

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